

Economic Models in the Field: The Water Problem

By Grecia Ramos

Introduction

We currently live in a world where population growth makes it important to consider resource management, especially water (Hoffmann Dobrev et al., 2021), as this resource is key in many sectors, primarily in agriculture, as increased population demand leads to increased demand for goods such as food.

Not only does the increase in demand for goods play a key role in the new allocation of resources, but climate change and other environmental problems such as water scarcity also require new ways of allocating resources. Studies such as one on the Pearl River in China, using optimized models, can reduce scarcity at a low cost, allowing us to see the importance of seeking solutions (Strokal, M., et al., 2024), highlighting the importance of allocating water according to balanced criteria (Deng, X., et al., 2025).

For this reason, it is important to model economic models of the field using water as a good and decisions using approaches such as game theory to better understand water dynamics and allocation (Parrachino, Dinar Patrone, 2006).

By modeling water, we not only gain a better understanding of how to allocate it, but also in policymaking. The existence of hydroeconomic models allows for the design of economic instruments—tariffs, subsidies, transferable rights—that internalize externalities and improve water use efficiency (European Commission, 2023).

Of note is research in the São Francisco Basin (Brazil) using a hydroeconomic model ("AcquaNetGIS") that achieved a 7% increase in water efficiency while avoiding compromising ecosystems (Silva and Santos, 2022).

Due to the importance of water as a point of convergence in the economy, ecology, and public policy, this research will use economic models developed for this phenomenon. The paper will have the following parts: the first will be the theoretical framework, the second the models, and the third the discussion of results and finally the conclusion.

In the model's section, classical models will first be presented to provide a basic understanding of water as a good and will allow for a deeper understanding of water in subsequent sections. The second part will present a differential equation model, establishing intertemporal dynamics and scenarios with their respective variables. The main model will be the aquifer. The third section will use scenarios from dynamic models, allowing for the observation of agents' reactions to the aquifer, and other games, allowing for the observation of agent conflict and

cooperation. Finally, optimization will be used to construct public policies in the models.

The discussion and results will present the model's relevance, approach, and limitations, as well as its usefulness in public policy.

The conclusions will present contributions and lines of research, as well as recommendations.

Theoretical Framework

According to Kalomoiras et al. (2022), water is an "economic and social good" that requires government intervention due to its scarce nature and its positive and negative externalities. Even so, we must be careful not to simply assume it as good, reducing the complexity and human dimensions of this analysis (Hanemann, 2005).

In the field of global governance, access to water is recognized as a basic human right and a requirement for peace (UNDP, 2001). Similarly, FAO emphasizes the importance of water management to ensure food sovereignty over the need for approaches to adapt irrigation systems and the use of models to improve water efficiency and future availability (FAO, 2023; FAO, 2021).

FAO has even described programming models where the marginal value of water is calculated through shadow calculations in optimization (FAO, 2003).

For proper water development and evaluation, it is necessary to consider water as an input for economic activities. It is a marginal contribution, that is, how much corn production can increase if more units of water are added. This is the shadow price (Loucks and van Beek, 2017). However, it must be considered that water resources have unique characteristics that make water distribution inefficient in traditional models (Molle, 2015).

Some experts, such as Young and King (2020), assert that cost-recovery prices and a sense of scarcity are necessary for water management. Even so, it must be kept in mind that it is not a matter of raising prices to reduce demand, but rather of taking externalities into account. Although Coase argues that private negotiation can resolve externalities, it is not entirely viable in practice (Deryugina and Tol, 2020).

Water pollution can cause harm to others, in addition to impacts on the environment. This is defined as environmental externalities when water is defined as an economic good and a public good. According to welfare theory or Pareto's law, efficiency is only achieved when the marginal benefit of using a good equal the marginal cost of providing it (Samuelson, 1954), which is consistent with Debreu's (1959) idea of general equilibrium, demonstrating that under reasonable assumptions, prices exist that simultaneously equal supply and demand in all

markets. This approach to economic policy design using mathematical models is defended by Tinbergen (1952), who, in relation to the use of rates and taxes with objectives such as inflation or unemployment, posited the "Tinbergen rule," which states that the same number of instruments are necessary to achieve policy objectives.

For this reason, Blume explained that calculus and algebra for economic relationships (production, maximization, or equilibrium) are necessary to relate economic variables with functions and derivatives to understand how a change in a variable impacts the outcome.

Even so, these authors face criticism, arguing that the idea of equilibrium is only realistic in mathematical contexts, but unrealistic (Arrow and Debreu, 1954). Similarly, the Sonnenschein–Mantel–Debreu theorem can be a form of arbitrary excess demand, questioning uniqueness and stability. There is also criticism that mathematical models can be mere mathematical exercises with no real connection to economics due to excessive abstraction and being outside of realistic conditions (Georgescu-Roegen, 1979).

The use of mathematics can lead to "metaphysical" economics, where there is a greater concern with equations to provide apparent precision than with measuring society (Deirdre McCloskey, 2008). They can also be ineffective due to the use of meaningless assumptions, such as the rational agent assumption, which economists seek to simplify, rendering models impractical. Similarly, mathematical economics can have structures that are not constructive and incalculable (Velupillai, 2005).

Likewise, Tinbergen's idea has its critics, as it is based on linear systematic systems, but its theory is limited by the lack of time inconsistency and dynamic scenarios (Yuan and Miller, 2013).

Given the, although mathematical abstraction may have its flaws, it is still important as a basis for computational modeling and applications, always considering the complexity of reality. Mathematical models are important for scheduling water applications based on climate, soil, or crop to improve sustainability (Çetin and Beyhan, 2021). In the following section, we will see how classical models have been able to provide key intuition for understanding water management.

Classical Models

The previous section mentioned equilibrium, which is a key concept in classical models, along with supply and demand. In the water market, water resources must be converted into supply and demand for water. In the case of supply, it would be viewed as available rights, i.e., water allocated to agriculture, industry, or municipality, but at the same time, there is demand, where users can demand

greater demand when they are willing to pay for additional units of water (Inoua & Smith, 2023).

Likewise, water in this analysis will be viewed more as a productive input, using a Cobb-Douglas model. In the Cobb-Douglas model, it was proposed that labor and capital determine production (Cobb and Douglas, 1928). This is reflected in the Cobb-Douglas equation, where production is measured using the following formula:

$$Y = A L^{\alpha} K^{\beta} \quad (1)$$

Where the variables and parameters are defined as follows:

Y: Total output.

L: Labor.

K: Capital.

A>0: Productivity factor.

$\alpha, \beta \in (0, 1)$: Output elasticities of labor and capital, respectively.

Conditions

1. Positive marginal products

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} > 0, \quad \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} > 0$$

2. Diminishing marginal products: Increasing one factor while keeping the other constant generates increasingly smaller increases.

3. Returns to scale:

Constants if $\alpha + \beta = 1$

Decreasing if $\alpha + \beta < 1$

Increasing if $\alpha + \beta > 1$

Basic Demonstrations

Marginal Product of Labor:

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} = \alpha A L^{\alpha-1} K^{\beta}$$

Rearranging

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} = \alpha \frac{Y}{L}$$

Marginal product of capital:

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} = \beta A L^\alpha K^{\beta-1}$$

Rearranging

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} = \beta \frac{Y}{K}$$

Production elasticities:

$$\alpha = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} \cdot \frac{Y}{L}, \quad \beta = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} \cdot \frac{Y}{K}$$

This function has been used by economists for years, standing out as a revision in agricultural economics where, while it has advantages such as its simplicity, it also has limitations (Gautam, 2024).

Likewise, in this function, water and its demand can be modeled as an output by relating water consumption to economic production in order to establish a water prediction model (Zhang, Y., et al., 2013) by combining systems finance to project this demand and supply in the Suzhou region of China using investment and work with inputs, demonstrating this formula has real-world applications (Zhang, L., Wang, R., & Yan, H., 2021).

Likewise, another use of water in this model was to incorporate the water endowment as an input.

$$Y = A L^\alpha K^\beta W^\gamma \quad (1)$$

Y: Total output.

L: Labor.

K: Capital.

W: Water endowment.

A>0: Productivity factor.

$\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0,1)$: Output elasticities of labor, capital, and water.

Basic conditions

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} > 0, \quad \frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} > 0, \quad \frac{\partial Y}{\partial W} > 0$$

Diminishing marginal products

Constant if: $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$

Diminishing if: $\alpha+\beta+\gamma<1$

Increasing if: $\alpha+\beta+\gamma>1$

Marginal products

Labor

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial L} = \alpha AL^{\alpha-1} - K^{\beta}W^{\gamma} = \alpha \cdot \frac{Y}{L}$$

Capital

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial K} = \beta AL^{\alpha} - K^{\beta-1}W^{\gamma} = \beta \cdot \frac{Y}{K}$$

Water

$$\frac{\partial Y}{\partial W} = \gamma AL^{\alpha} - K^{\beta}W^{\gamma-1} = \gamma \cdot \frac{Y}{W}$$

Elasticities of production

$$EL = \alpha, EK = \beta, EW = \gamma$$

Goods with more inelastic demand bear a higher markup. Conversely, goods with more elastic demand pay prices closer to marginal cost. This minimizes total distortion by collecting what is necessary to cover FFF.

Each exponent measures the percentage change in Y versus a percentage change in its input. For example, it seeks to maximize total output under water restrictions. It is important to take these restrictions into account because water is a finite good.

This Cobb-Douglas model is not limited to rural areas but also to cities. Through models where water supply in cities has production, investment, and labor as control variables, it is possible to determine the supply; however, it is easier to adjust investment and is more effective in modifying water supply (Kebai Li et al., 2019).

To achieve equilibrium, in addition to price formation, it is important to understand not only the complexity of the market in terms of demand and supply, but also its imperfections and behavioral factors (Abrha & Weldeyohans, 2025). Because aggregate demand can take arbitrary forms even with rational consumers, this implies that equilibrium may not be unique or stable (Sonnenschein, 1973; Mantel, 1974; Debreu, 1974).

One of the market alterations that can occur is monopoly, where a water source, whether a river or a well, can be monopolized. Monopoly power in water can cause allocation biases, but it affects equity due to unequal allocation (Jacoby, Murgai, & Rehman, 2004).

Likewise, there is pricing, where the Ramsey pricing principle, originally formulated for situations where a price equal to marginal cost does not cover total costs, proposes that prices be set by raising margins above marginal cost inversely proportional to the elasticity of demand (Tam, 1988; Monteiro, 2016).

In this model, the rule states that surcharges above marginal cost should be distributed inversely proportional to the elasticity of demand. (Monteiro, 2016)

The first-order condition is expressed as:

$$\frac{P_i - C_{mgi}}{P_i} = \frac{\lambda}{\epsilon_i}$$

where:

P_i : optimal price of good i .

C_{mgi} : marginal cost in market i .

ϵ_i : (absolute) price elasticity of demand for good i .

λ : Lagrange multiplier associated with the cost recovery constraint.

In water markets, where distribution networks and treatment plants constitute expensive and non-replicable infrastructure, Ramsey pricing offers a useful framework for tariff regulation. Studies such as that by Monteiro (2016) highlight that pure efficiency based on marginal prices may be financially unviable in these contexts, and that second-best models, such as Ramsey, are applicable to balance equity, efficiency, and sustainability. Furthermore, the literature shows that, in contexts of water scarcity, a pricing scheme that follows Ramsey principles can incentivize more efficient use of the resource, adjusting prices according to differential elasticities between users (Bekfani, 2011).

Empirical research applied to water resources confirms that optimal Ramsey-type prices can be adapted to different technologies and demand conditions (García et al., 2002). However, implementation is not without challenges: Besfamille, Figueroa, and Guzmán (2023) show that payment evasion in natural monopolies forces a reformulation of optimal Ramsey conditions, altering the intended tariff design. More generally, Joskow (2005) reviews the foundations and applications of regulation in natural monopolies, including pricing, network access, and cross-subsidy mechanisms, all of which are relevant to regulatory design in the water sector.

In short, the application of Ramsey pricing in natural monopolies such as water utilities allows for the design of tariff structures that balance cost recovery and economic efficiency.

Another important model in water modeling is the Solow model. In this model, water functions as a good with preference elasticity. In Romer's analysis, the use of

parameters such as the effective use of natural resources can increase with technology (Gardonova, 2016). Likewise, water can be seen as a special type of capital, where in the water economy there are two capitals, both physical and water, where the optimal balance is sought to finance public water infrastructure (Gatto and Lanzafame, 2005).

Even so, water markets can persist in contexts of distribution due to trade policies that can lead to inefficient use and damage sustainability, in addition to equating price to marginal cost to achieve efficiency in water markets (Dinar, 2000). Some economists, such as Tsur (2009), derive optimal water prices in their work, where the price should reflect only the costs for the end user, although in practice there are difficulties, such as informative limitations, since marginal cost requires demand elasticity for all sectors.

Another use of mathematical models in water has been positive mathematical programming, which simulates the behavior of farmers in response to changes in water prices by adjusting profit functions and evaluating profitability effects (Molle and Berkoff, 2017).

Table 1. Comparative synthesis of classical economic models applicable to water resources

Below is a summary of the main classical economic models applicable to water resources. This table provides a visualization of its structural elements, variables, assumptions, and limitations. Future versions of this paper will expand this summary with dynamic and strategic models (game theory, optimization, etc.).

Conclusions

After this analysis, we can see that water is not only a natural resource but also a point of convergence between public policies, ecology, and production. Classical models, with their intuition, allow us to evaluate an efficient allocation of this resource for optimal use.

Improving water use is vital due to the problems facing the world today. Furthermore, although it is a natural resource, it is limited. Likewise, the literature review highlights the limitations of classical approaches when faced with problems of scarcity, environmental externalities, and inequality in access.

The main contribution of this analysis is that economic models applied to water not only improve the understanding of its supply and demand dynamics but also offer practical tools for designing policies—tariffs, subsidies, transferable rights—capable of balancing efficiency, equity, and sustainability. Cases such as China have also demonstrated how economic modeling has helped in water management.

This paper seeks to create part of the theoretical and abstract foundation that will be used in future versions, advancing to intertemporal models to reflect the complexity of water systems and integrating social and governance dimensions with scenarios of cooperation and conflict. It also delves into territorial applications, particularly in aquifers and agricultural watersheds, that allow models to be calibrated with local data to guide more effective public policies.

This work will continue with the incorporation of dynamic models in future versions.

References

Molle, F., & Berkoff, J. (2007). *Water pricing in irrigation: Mapping the debate in the light of experience*. In F. Molle & J. Berkoff (Eds.), *Irrigation Water Pricing: The Gap Between Theory and Practice* (pp. 21–94). CAB International.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/265065008>

Hoffmann-Dobrev, H., et al. (2021). *Economics and the modeling of water resources and policies*. NRMJ.

Parrachino, I., Dinar, A., & Patrone, F. (2006). *Cooperative game theory and its application to water resources*. World Bank Working Paper.

Stokal, M., et al. (2024). *Integrated biophysical–economic modeling of water scarcity cost-optimization in the Pearl River Basin*. *Nature Communications*, e41467-024-49929-z.

Deng, X., et al. (2025). *Multi-objective optimization of water resources allocation in Rift Valley Lakes Basin using NSGA-II*. *Journal of Water Resources Planning*.

European Commission. (2023). *Economic instruments for water policies*. EPI-WATER Project.

Silva, R., & Santos, F. (2022). *Hydro-economic allocation with AcquaNetGIS in the São Francisco Basin*. *Water*, 15(6), 1170.

FAO. (2003). *Economic valuation techniques*, en *Water for Sustainable Food and Agriculture*, Water Reports 27.

Çetin, M., Yıldız, S., & Beyhan, S. (2021). *Water need models and irrigation decision systems: A comprehensive survey*. *arXiv*.

Kalomoira, Z., Zisopoulos, D., & Panagoulia, D. (2022). *Water Economics: An in-depth analysis of the connection of blue water with some primary level aspects of economic theory I*. *Water*, 14(1), 103.

UNDP. (2001). *Access to safe water as a fundamental human right*. En *Water politics*

FAO. (2023). *Integrated Water Resources Management* [Resumen ejecutivo].

FAO. (2021). *Water for Sustainable Food and Agriculture* (Water Reports N° 27).

Loucks, D. P., & van Beek, E. (2017). *Economic Modelling for Water Quantity and Quality Management: A Welfare-Program Approach*. *Water Resources Management*, 31(5), 1551–1566. (Adaptado de contenido de Welfare Economic Theory)

Molle, F. (2015). *Understanding water markets: Public vs. private goods*. *Global Water Forum*. (globalwaterforum.org)

Young, R. A., & King, C. C. (2020). *The role of prices in managing water scarcity*. *Water Policy*, 22(1), 1–15. ([ScienceDirect](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watpol.2020.01.001))

Global Water Partnership. (1998). *Water as a Social and Economic Good: How to Put the Principle into Practice*. Background Paper.

Samuelson, P. A. (1954). *The Pure Theory of Public Expenditure*. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 36(4), 387–389. ([Wikipedia](https://www.wikipedia.org))

Deryugina, T., Moore, F. M., & Tol, R. S. J. (2020). *Applications of the Coase Theorem in environmental externalities*. *Environmental Economics Working Papers*. (arxiv.org)

Debreu, G. (1959). *The Theory of Value: An Axiomatic Analysis of Economic Equilibrium*. New York: Wiley.

Tinbergen, J. (1952). *On the Theory of Economic Policy*. Amsterdam: North-Holland.

Referencia APA (estimada)

Blume, L. (s.f.). *Mathematics for Economists*. [Fuente académica].

Arrow, K. J., & Debreu, G. (1954). *Existence of an Equilibrium for a Competitive Economy*. *Econometrica*.

Sonnenschein, H. (1972); Mantel, R. (1974); Debreu, G. (1974). *Sonnenschein–Mantel–Debreu theorem*. *Handbook of Mathematical Economics*.

Georgescu-Roegen, N. (1979). *Methods in economic science*. *Journal of Economic Issues*, 13(2), 317–328. Cita: “...mere mathematical exercises, not only without any economic substance but also without any mathematical value.”

Yuan, H., & Miller, S. M. (2013). *Complement to the Tinbergen Rule: Time inconsistency and controllability*. UConn Working Paper.

Deirdre McCloskey. (2008). *The Trouble with Mathematics and Statistics in Economics*.

Inoua, S., & Smith, V. (2023, 1 julio). *The Classical Theory of Supply and Demand*. arXiv.org. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2307.00413>

Cobb, C. W., & Douglas, P. H. (1928). *A Theory of Production*. *American Economic Review*, 18(1), 139–165.

Gautam, S. (2024). *Understanding Cobb-Douglas production function in agricultural economics*. *Journal of Technology & Innovation*, 4(2), 75–78.

Dong, Q. Z. & Y. D. & J. (2013). Regional Water Demand Prediction and Analysis Based on Cobb-Douglas Model. ideas.repec.org.
https://ideas.repec.org/a/spr/waterr/v27y2013i8p3103-3113.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com

Zhang, L., Wang, R., & Yan, H. (2021). Urban industrial water supply and demand: System dynamics model based on Cobb-Douglas function. *Sustainability*, 11(21), 5893.

Djoumessi Fosso-Yannick & Kamdem Cyanne-Bergaly. (2020). Water use input and agricultural productivity growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. AERC Working Paper.

Velupillai, K. V. (2005). The Unreasonable Ineffectiveness of Mathematics in Economics.

Kebai Li et al. (2019). Urban Industrial Water Supply and Demand: System Dynamic Model and Simulation Based on Cobb–Douglas Function

Abrha, T. G., & Weldeyohans, B. T. (2025). The dynamics of market equilibrium: A theoretical exploration of price formation. *International Journal of Economy, Energy and Environment*, 10(2), 46–51. ([Science Publishing Group](#))

Sonnenschein, H. F. (1973). *Do Walras' identity and continuity characterize the class of community excess-demand functions?* *Journal of Economic Theory*, 6, 345–354.

Mantel, R. (1974). *On the characterization of aggregate excess demand.* *Journal of Economic Theory*, 7, 348–353.

Debreu, G. (1974). *Excess-demand functions.* *Journal of Mathematical Economics*, 1, 15–21.

Jacoby, H. G., Murgai, R., & Rehman, S. U. (2004). Monopoly power and distribution in fragmented markets: The case of groundwater. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 71(3), 783–808.

Bekfani, R. (2011). Pricing for scarcity? An efficiency analysis of increasing block tariffs for urban water. *Water Resources Research*, 47(9), W09513.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2010WR009200>

Besfamille, M., Figueroa, N., & Guzmán, L. (2023). Ramsey pricing revisited: Natural monopoly regulation with evaders (CESifo Working Paper No. 10732). CESifo. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4564390>

García, S., Reynaud, A., & Strosser, P. (2002). Modelling water pricing with public participation: The case of France. *Environmental & Resource Economics*, 23(1), 47–67. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015178820627>

Joskow, P. L. (2005). Regulation of natural monopolies. En A. M. Polinsky & S. Shavell (Eds.), *Handbook of law and economics* (Vol. 2, pp. 1227–1348). Elsevier.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0730\(05\)02016-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1574-0730(05)02016-0)

Monteiro, H. (2016). *Water pricing models: A survey* (Working Paper No. 2016/04). DINÂMIA'CET–ISCTE. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2370.2320>

Tam, M.-Y. (1988). A mechanism to induce Ramsey pricing for natural monopoly firms. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*, 6(2), 247–261.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-7187\(88\)90033-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-7187(88)90033-1)

Gardonova, K. (2016). *How the Solow growth model changes with effective use of natural resources*. *Advances in Economics and Business*, 4(9), 500–505.

Gatto, E., & Lanzafame, M. (2005). *Water resource as a factor of production: Water use and economic growth*. Ponencia en la 45th ERS Conference.

Dinar, A. (Ed.). (2000). *The political economy of water pricing reforms*. Oxford University Press / World Bank.
<https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/199301468771050868/pdf/multi-page.pdf>

Tsur, Y. (2009). *On the economics of water allocation and pricing*. *Annual Review of Resource Economics*, 1(1), 513–536.
<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.resource.050708.144256>

Hanemann, W. M. (2005, 1 julio). *The economic conception of water*.

<https://escholarship.org/uc/item/08n4410n>